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Mixed Ligand Complexes of bis(Thenoyl Trifluoro Acetonato) and bis(Pivaloyl Trifluoro Acetonato) Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Heterocyclic Nitrogen Bases

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CHEMISTRY of metal β -diketonates has invoked lots of interest¹ in recent years in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas chromatography, solvent extraction, column and thin layer chromatography, nmr shift reagents, laser technology and as initiators in polymerisation reactions. Bis(β -diketonato) metal(II) complexes behave as Lewis acids and form five or six coordinate adducts with neutral donor molecule². The stability of an adduct depends both on the basicity of the β -diketonates and that of a neutral ligand. Introduction of an electron withdrawing group such as CF₃ into β -diketone increases the affinity of a central metal ion for ligation³. Formation of adducts of metal β -diketone chelates plays an important role in the synergistic enhancement of solvent extraction of metal ions^{4,5}. The quasi aromatic character of such compounds has also received considerable attention. Earlier, we reported⁶⁻⁹ many five coordinated nitrogen base adducts of copper(II) and zinc(II) β -diketonates and also the adducts^{10,11} of γ -substituted copper(II) β -diketonates. This communication reports the mixed ligand complexes of the type M(tta)₂B and M(pta)₂B where M=Cu(II), Zn(II); B is a nitrogen base and tta and pta are the anions of thenoyltrifluoroacetone and pivaloyltrifluoro acetone, respectively.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metal chelates were prepared by reacting aqueous solutions of the respective metal acetates with ethanol solution of the β -diketonates in 1 : 2 proportion. The chelates were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

Base adducts of zinc were prepared by refluxing the β -diketonates with the nitrogen bases (1 : 2) in methanol for 30 min and cooling the resulting solution overnight. Adducts of copper(II) β -diketonates

were prepared by warming the β -diketonates in excess of base in presence of small amount of chloroform and cooling the solution overnight in a refrigerator. The compounds were dried in vacuum.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M acetone solution of the complexes by Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic moments were measured on solid specimens at 25° by Guoy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 621 and 337 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were measured in 10⁻³ M (chloroform+base) solution using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The data are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compounds	Conduc- tance mhos.cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis%; Found(Calcd.)	
			metal	nitrogen
1. CuL ₂ Q	9.5	1.79	9.63 (10.0)	1.98 (2.21)
2. CuL ₂ (IQ)	8.8	1.80	9.72 (10.0)	1.95 (2.21)
3. CuL ₂ (pip)	8.5	1.78	10.52 (10.75)	1.98 (2.37)
4. CuL ₂ (Morph)	7.8	1.78	10.58 (10.79)	2.02 (2.38)
5. CuL ₂ (Quin)	11.2	1.82	9.45 (9.79)	1.81 (2.16)
6. ZnL ₂ Q	10.6	—	9.86 (10.26)	1.83 (2.20)
7. ZnL ₂ (IQ)	10.5	—	9.88 (10.26)	1.85 (2.20)
8. ZnL ₂ (pip)	11.8	—	10.85 (11.03)	2.01 (2.36)
9. ZnL ₂ (Morph)	12.4	—	10.82 (11.07)	2.02 (2.37)
10. ZnL ₂ (Quin)	8.9	—	9.75 (10.05)	1.91 (2.15)
11. CuL' ₂ Q	8.8	1.82	10.72 (10.90)	2.28 (2.40)
12. CuL' ₂ (IQ)	7.8	1.81	10.68 (10.90)	2.25 (2.40)
13. CuL' ₂ (pip)	9.5	1.79	11.45 (11.78)	2.30 (2.60)
14. CuL' ₂ (Morph)	9.8	1.80	11.61 (11.84)	2.32 (2.61)
15. CuL' ₂ (Quin)	10.1	1.79	10.32 (10.65)	2.05 (2.35)
16. ZnL' ₂ Q	10.4	—	10.85 (11.18)	2.01 (2.39)
17. ZnL' ₂ (IQ)	11.3	—	10.78 (11.18)	1.98 (2.39)
18. ZnL' ₂ (pip)	11.5	—	11.76 (12.09)	2.38 (2.59)
19. ZnL' ₂ (Morph)	8.9	—	11.78 (12.14)	2.34 (2.60)
20. ZnL' ₂ (Quin)	8.5	—	10.61 (10.92)	2.05 (2.34)

L₁=anion of thenoyltrifluoroacetone.

L'₁=anion of pivaloyltrifluoroacetone.

Q = quinoline, IQ = Isoquinoline, pip = piperidine,

Morph = Morpholine, Quin = Quinaldine.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the general formula M(tta)₂B or M(pta)₂B.

Copper(II) complexes are green crystalline, whereas zinc complexes are white crystalline compounds. They have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the low molar conductance values indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic moments of copper(II) complexes are in the range of 1.78-1.82 B.M. showing the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a $3d^9$ ion.

Infrared spectra: In case of the thenoyltrifluoroacetone chelates two bands appear around 1605 and 1580 cm^{-1} region of which the high frequency band can be assigned to carbonyl stretching vibration. There is also an absorption band around 3500 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the coordinated water molecule. In the nitrogen base adducts the carbonyl stretching band shifts to 1620 cm^{-1} in case of zinc complexes whereas two bands appear at 1615 and 1605 cm^{-1} in case of copper(II) complexes, alongwith the disappearance of O-H stretching band due to the water molecule. Further, most of the absorption bands of the free nitrogen ligands are shifted in the base adducts, providing evidence of bonding through the nitrogen atom of the bases. In case of the pivaloyltrifluoroacetone chelates, carbonyl stretching appears as a broad absorption band at 1600 cm^{-1} , due to the presence of $\delta(\text{OH})$ in this region alongwith the $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ appearing at 3480 cm^{-1} . In the mixed ligand complexes the carbonyl absorption appears as a sharp band around 1620-25 cm^{-1} region instead of the broad band of the *bis* chelate and the absorption due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ disappears, thus indicating the coordination of the nitrogen ligands to the metal ion. This has been further substantiated by the observations^{1,2} of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 390-440 and 280-310 cm^{-1} regions, respectively. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ shifts to high frequency region in the base adducts and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ shifts to low frequency region compared to the simple chelates. Further, compared to the non-fluorinated β -diketone chelates and the base adducts, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in the present compounds shifts to high frequency region and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ to low frequency region.

In the visible electronic spectra of copper(II) chelates and their base adducts one broad absorption band has been observed. $\text{Cu}(\text{tta})_2$ showed absorption at 680 nm ($\epsilon=30$), whereas in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{pta})_2$ the band was observed at 670 nm ($\epsilon=35$). In the base adducts, the absorption band was observed around 690-710 nm region with an increase in the intensity of the band ($\epsilon=60-80$). This is in agreement with many earlier observations. Thus in general there is^{1,3-15} a low frequency shift of the absorption band and increase in intensity of the band on adduct formation compared to the simple *bis* chelates.

Hence the base adducts of copper(II) and zinc β -diketonate are presumably penta-coordinated compounds formed by the coordination of one molecule of the nitrogen base to the metal *bis* chelates. To verify that the base adducts are actually five coordinated monomers rather than 6-coordinated dimers,

the molecular weights of the compounds $\text{Cu}(\text{tta})_2(\text{Q})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{pta})_2(\text{Q})$ were determined by vapour pressure osmometric method in benzene. The observed molecular weights are 602 and 554, calculated values being 634.92 and 582.88, respectively indicating the complexes to be monomeric. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data of the zinc complexes, these are possibly five-coordinated compounds similar to some earlier reported^{1,6} complexes.

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Determination of Stability Constants of Some Metal Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-methylchalkone Oxime (HMMCO)

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THE formation constants of some bivalent metal ion chelates with 2-hydroxychalkone and 2-hydroxy-5'-methylchalkone in 70% v/v ethanol-water mixture were reported by Swamy *et al*¹. Khadikar *et al*² also studied the formation constants of some bivalent metal ion chelates with 2'-hydroxychalkone in 60% v/v dioxane-water mixture. The present work deals with the determination of successive stability constants of complexes of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) with some transition metal ions in 50% dioxane-water mixture at 25° and